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Editor

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**DEPARTMENT OF WEST ASIAN
AND NORTH AFRICAN STUDIES
ALIGARH MUSLIM UNIVERSITY
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JOURNAL OF WEST ASIAN STUDIES

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EDITORIAL

It gives me immense pleasure to present before you the volume thirty five of the Journal of West Asian Studies. Journal of West Asian Studies is an annual publication of the Department of West Asian Studies published uninterrupted since last thirty five years. It is concerned with the various cultural, economic, historical political and social issues, both contemporary and past of the West Asian region. Continuous efforts have been made to improve the quality of the Journal. For the articles to be accepted for publication original contribution, systematic and scientific methodology, the scholarly rigour and contribution to the existing stock of knowledge certified by the referees have been the sole criteria for the acceptance of papers for publication. This volume consists of 18 papers concerned with the divergent issues of the region which is termed as West Asia.

The first paper in this volume by Girijesh Pant and Vrushal Ghoble deals with an important issue which is Saudi Arabia's political economy of geo-economic shift. It says that the socioeconomic pressures have triggered the laying of foundations of knowledge economy. It expects generation of participatory phenomenon resulting in some devolution of power. The second paper by Muhammad Azhar discusses Indians in Qatar. Indians constitute the largest segment of population in Qatar even more than the nationals. Qatar has been a success story for Indians but not without associated problems. The third paper by Rakhshanda F. Fazli and Rashid Aziz Faridi discusses the various aspects of return migrant's perceptions towards infrastructure, labour efficiency and Capital management in India. The fourth paper is by Jajati K. Patnaik and Chandan K. Panda. They have tried to assess the efficacy of consociationalism in Lebanon. The fifth paper by Fasih Raghbir Gauhar analyses the effectiveness of Jordan's diplomacy in dealing with regional crisis. The sixth paper by Azizur Rahman Azami offers a discussion on the Peshmerga women, the women wing of the Peshmerga, the Kurdish armed forces. The seventh paper by Atikur-Rahman deals with culture as a determinant in India-GCC relations. The eighth paper authored by Ziaur Rahman analyses the ideas of the Arab nation, Arab nationalism and pan Arab Unity.

The ninth paper by Syed Mohammad Raghieb is an effort to study the changing contours of India-Jordan relations. In the tenth paper Saddam Hussain and Nghma Farooqui have tried to study the Kurdish problem through the realist perspective. The eleventh paper by Saima Farhat studies the emerging trade nexus between India and United Arab Emirates before the Covid 19. The twelfth paper by Imtiaz Ahmad traces the historical and other dimensions of Yemeni diaspora. While Ankita Sanyal in her papers, thirteenth in line, studies Syrian women's attempt at state reconstruction since 2011. The fourteenth paper by Sana Noor and Haris Noor analyses the flow of FDI between India and the United Arab Emirates. The fifteenth paper by Alamgir Husain and Salina Akhtar studies Saudi Arabia's trade diplomacy specially in the context of India in the twenty first century. The sixteenth paper by Mohd Waseem and Haris Noor discusses the impact of Saudi Vision 2030 and the knowledge economy on non-Saudi workers. Further, there are two short papers included in the Notes and Discussions section. The paper by Sana Samreen analyses the usage of CHATGPT and its implications on the major oil exporting Countries of West Asia. While the paper by Shaik Sadiq Ulla Hussain analyses the opportunities and challenges of India-Qatar relations. This volume also includes a review of the book "Rethinking U.S. Education Policy: Paradigms of the Knowledge Economy" by Mohd Waseem. In my opinion the Journal of West Asian Studies has a lot to offer to the researcher and others interested in the West Asian region. I wish readers find this volume beneficial, interesting, insightful and useful for their academic pursuits and encourage them to consider this journal for publishing their valuable research. I express my sincere gratitude to all the anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments, suggestions and cooperation in ensuring the academic standard and timely publication of the Journals. I would be failing in my duty if I do not acknowledge the contributions of Associate editors Prof. Jawaid Iqbal and Prof. Rakhshanda Fazli. I am also thankful to the Vice-Chancellor of Aligarh Muslim University Prof. Mohd. Gulrez for his constant support and encouragement. Lastly I must acknowledge the dedicated support of the research scholars of the department, specially Mohd Waseem at every stage of the publication of this issue of the journal.

Muhammad Azher
Editor

BOOK REVIEW

Rethinking U.S. Education Policy: *Paradigms of the Knowledge Economy*, Daniel Araya, Palgrave Macmillan; 2015, 184 pages, ISBN 978-1137475558

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The book “Rethinking U.S. Education Policy: Paradigms of the Knowledge Economy” by Daniel Araya explores the intersection of education policy and economic imperatives in the United States. The book is structured into six chapters, each addressing different aspects of this intersection. These chapters set the stage for understanding how education policy in the U.S. has been influenced and shaped by economic considerations, reflecting on historical and contemporary trends. The Second chapter delves into the concept of the knowledge economy, defining it and examining its implications for education and policy-making. The third chapter explores different models or frameworks within the knowledge economy, discussing how each paradigm influences education policy. The fourth chapter assesses the education policies implemented during Obama's presidency, analysing their alignment with the knowledge economy paradigms. The next chapter possibly presents a discussion or critique of the concept of the knowledge economy, examining alternative viewpoints or the dialogue surrounding this economic model. The last concluding chapter presumably synthesises the insights from the previous chapters, offering recommendations or new perspectives on how U.S. education policy can be rethought or reformed in the context of the knowledge economy.

The introduction of “Rethinking U.S. Education Policy: Paradigms of the Knowledge Economy” by Daniel Araya sets the stage for the book's exploration of the dynamic relationship between education policy and the economic imperatives in the United States. It outlines the central theme of how education policy is increasingly intertwined with economic goals, particularly within the context of the knowledge economy. This section provides an overview of the subsequent chapters' key arguments, theoretical frameworks, and objectives, framing the discussion within the broader socio-economic landscape. The first chapter, “U.S. Education Policy as Economic Policy,” examines the relationship between U.S. education policy and economic policy. It critically analyses the prevailing assumptions and paradigms that shape educational reform policies in the context of the knowledge economy. The chapter argues that there are contradictory readings of the knowledge economy within educational reform policies, highlighting the need to reexamine the fundamental assumptions guiding U.S. education policy. It emphasises the importance of understanding the different conceptualisations of the knowledge economy as they produce contradictory policy narratives. Finally, the first chapter comprehensively analyses how economic policy influences U.S. education policy, challenging existing assumptions and advocating for evaluating policy narratives in light of the knowledge economy. In “The Knowledge Economy in Context,” the second chapter focuses on defining and understanding the concept of the knowledge economy. This chapter may explore the knowledge economy's origins, development, and characteristics, illustrating how it differs from traditional economic models. The author also discusses the implications of the knowledge economy for education, mainly how it necessitates a shift in educational approaches and policies to align with new economic demands. This chapter probably examines different interpretations of what constitutes a knowledge economy, how it functions, and its

implications for society, particularly in education and workforce development.

The chapter “Education Policy and the Obama Administration” discusses the Obama Administration's education policy under the “A Strategy for American Innovation: Securing Our Economic Growth and Prosperity” framework. This policy, developed by the National Economic Council, the Council of Economic Advisers, and the Office of Science and Technology Policy, emphasises the government's role in steering the U.S. innovation system, highlighting the importance of public investment in innovation as critical to catalysing the U.S. economy. The Obama Administration's education policy centres on creating an internationally competitive and innovative educational system, investing in scientific research and developing first-class infrastructure. These elements are considered the building blocks of an innovation strategy that aims to propel America forward in a knowledge-intensive economy. The policy also promotes competitive markets through entrepreneurship, export promotion, regional cluster strategies, and catalysing technology breakthroughs in various sectors, including clean energy, healthcare technologies, education technology, and advanced manufacturing. This chapter probably evaluates how these policies aligned with or diverged from the paradigms of the knowledge economy, analysing their impact and effectiveness. It may also discuss the challenges and successes of these policies in shaping the U.S. education system to meet the demands of a rapidly evolving economic landscape. The chapter “The Knowledge Economy in Dialogue” explores diverse perspectives and debates surrounding the knowledge economy, addressing potential critiques and alternative viewpoints. It also examines the dialogue between educational stakeholders and the economy, offering a more nuanced understanding of the knowledge economy's implications for education policy.

“Rethinking U.S. Education Policy” does an insightful analysis. It primarily focuses on U.S. policy within a narrow economic framework, potentially neglecting the multifaceted nature of educational challenges. The book emphasises policy and economic perspectives, overshadowing educators' and students' practical realities and diverse classroom experiences. Furthermore, its strong alignment with specific economic theories limits its applicability to broader global educational contexts. Araya's significant critique is enhanced by adopting a more equitable method that includes a wider spectrum of educational theories and practices, extending beyond the economic perspective. However, this book proves to be an invaluable source for scholars seeking a comprehensive study of the knowledge economy.